

The Case of Bioethanol by using with Economic Assessment of Bio refinery Processes

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Bioethanol gained growing attention as biofuel in the recent past. Its production steadily increased over the years attesting on 87.2 billion liters worldwide in 2013, with the United States as the top producer (ca. 60%), followed by Brazil. Ethanol is mainly produced from sugar cane (Brazil) and corn or other cereals (US), but these sources induced criticisms as for social sustainability, being directly competitive with the food and feed chain. Therefore, a second generation concept was introduced for biofuels, by developing processes for their production from waste biomass or energy crops not competitive with agriculture. However, currently in the US and Europe most bioethanol is still produced as first generation. For example, it was estimated that in 2011, 40% of corn harvested in the US was used as a feedstock for bioethanol production, compared to just 7% a decade earlier. Early examples of second generation bioethanol production are available, such as the Proesa process developed by Mossi & Ghisolfi group in Italy [1]. This process commercially operated since 2013 for the production of 40 kton/year of bioethanol (60 kton/year at full capacity) starting mainly from Arundo Donax, a common cane which can be harvested locally with good yield. The same technology has been exported in Brazil (65 kton/year, from sugar cane transformation wastes) and US (60 kton/year from non-food competitive biomass). In April 2013, a commercial ethanol plant started being built in Florida using sweet sorghum as a feedstock. The plant is being built by Southeast Renewable Fuels LLC using the process technology of Uni-Systems do Brasil Ltd. In spite of these emerging commercial experience in biorefinery, a consolidated expertise is still lacking. In particular, in developing countries it will be a challenge to balance large-scale industrial development with small-scale local value chains, which would be required to ensure environmental, economical and social sustainability. Therefore, to

become a viable alternative, biofuels should be economically competitive, show environmental benefits, and provide a high net energy gain. On the other hand the research is very active in the biorefinery field. Simple queries on Scopus reveal that the word “biorefinery” is included in 3,646 references, “biofuels” in 37,193 documents and “bioethanol production” returns 4,859 references. As for bioethanol uses, the commercial practice is presently focused on the use of bioethanol as blend for gasoline or directly as fuel, to meet the most recent regulations on the fuel pool quota from renewable sources. Also in this case the research broadens the application potential of bioethanol, focusing mainly on hydrogen/syngas production by thermocatalytic processing (e.g., steam reforming) or on chemicals such as diethyl ether or ethylene. To date, comprehensive information on the economic sustainability of these ethanol conversion processes is still lacking. Indeed, in spite of huge efforts in developing materials and innovative ideas, the economical assessment of the proposed solutions is fundamentally lacking and this prevents the analysis on the real breakthrough potential of these technologies. Furthermore, no idea on the size of possible plants is given, to assess their real sustainability and possibility of integration in the social framework of different countries. Only few

Reports: Results address bioethanol production (mainly first generation) and much less its transformation into hydrogen through steam reforming. Some of the most recent examples of techno-economic assessment of bioethanol production/exploitation are described in the following. Brunet et al. described process simulation and optimised heat integration of bioethanol production from corn (40 million gal/year) [2]. Life-cycle analysis is also included. The estimated total capital investment of a dry-grind bioethanol production from corn was

60.5 million \$, the operating cost was 67.4 million \$/year. The most significant parameter was the cost of corn (92.96% of the raw materials), while the cost of utilities was 15.1 million \$/year. As for LCA, most of the environmental impact comes from the use of the corn (74.6%), followed by utilities. The energy required to obtain one gallon of bioethanol is estimated ca. 25 BTU, ca. 40% attributed to the reboiler of the beer column, rectifier and stripping.

Conclusion:The most developed processes for the production of lignocellulosic bioethanol are based on biomass pretreatment by dilute acid treatment, steam explosion or similar thermomechanical processes. Typically, in these cases lignin is recovered and valorised as fuel as a mean to economically sustain the process. A different concept is at the basis of the "Organosolv" process, which dissolves lignin in a proper organic solvent in order to recover it in pure form to be valorised as chemical or additive[3]. Some demonstrative scale processes have been developed and reviewed by Kautto et al. [3] with attention to the minimum ethanol selling price resulting from different technologies. Capital costs, annual cash flows and sensitivity analysis towards different parameters (technical and market-related) have been considered. Higher capital costs are associated to the organosolv process due to more complex layout. Therefore, profitability is excluded if lignin does not find a suitable market with much higher revenue than as fuel. A systematic framework for the design and assessment of bio-based chemical processes was proposed by Nguyen et al. [4] for the production of three commodity chemicals from ethanol: ethylene, acetic acid and ethylacetate. The starting biomass was also varied, including sugarcane, corn and corn stover. The paper interestingly compares not only the total production costs of the proposed commodities, but also the environmental impact and safety analysis.

Result: Different retrofit cases have been analysed considering a 40 kton/year ethanol production facility from corn, including fluctuating price of the raw material [5]. The results suggest that grain price is fundamental to determine the profitability of the

plant. Decreasing the

References

1. Cellulosic Ethanol Proesa, Biochemtex.
2. Brunet R, Boer D, Guillén-Gosálbez G, Jiménez L (2015) Reducing the cost, environmental impact and energy consumption of biofuel processes through heat integration. *Chem Eng Res Des* 93: 203-212.
3. Kautto J, Realff MJ, Ragauskas AJ, Kässi T (2014) Economic Analysis of an Organosolv Process for Bioethanol Production. *BioResources* 9: 6041-6072.
4. Nguyen TTH, Kikuchi Y, Noda M, Hirao M (2015) A New Approach for the Design and Assessment of Bio-based Chemical Processes toward Sustainability. *Ind Eng Chem Res* 54: 5494-5504.
5. Rajendran K, Rajoli S, Teichert O, Taherzadeh MJ (2014) Impacts of retrofitting analysis on first generation ethanol production: process design and techno-economics. *Bioprocess Biosyst Eng* 38: 389-397.
6. Rossetti I, Lasso J, Compagnoni M, Guido G De (2015) H₂ Production from Bioethanol and its Use in Fuel-Cells. *Chem Eng Trans* 43: 229-234.
7. Rossetti I, Compagnoni M, Torli M (2015) Process simulation and optimisation of H₂ production from ethanol steam reforming and its use in fuel cells. 1. Thermodynamic and kinetic analysis. *Chem Eng J*. 281: 1024-1035.
8. Rossetti I, Compagnoni M, Torli M (2015) Process simulation and optimization of H₂ production from ethanol steam reforming and its use in fuel cells. 2. Process analysis and optimization. *Chem Eng J*. 281: 1036-1044.
9. Ren J, Dong L, Sun L, Goodsite ME, Tan S, et al. (2015) Life cycle cost optimization of biofuel supply chains under uncertainties based on interval linear programming. *Bioresour Technol* 187: 6-13.
10. Mazzetto F, Simoes-Lucas G, Ortiz-Gutiérrez RA,

- Manca D, Bezzo F (2015) Impact on the optimal design of bioethanol supply chains by a new European Commission proposal. *Chem Eng Res Des* 93: 457-463.
11. Mazzetto F, Ortiz-Gutiérrez RA, Manca D, Bezzo F (2013) Strategic Design of Bioethanol Supply Chains Including Commodity Market Dynamics. *Ind Eng Chem Res* 52: 10305-10316.
12. Reyes Valle C, Villanueva Perales AL, Vidal-Barreiro F, Ollero P (2015) Integrated economic and life cycle assessment of thermochemical production of bioethanol to reduce production cost by exploiting excess of greenhouse gas savings. *Appl Energy* 148: 466-475.